

ETHICS IN EDUCATION AND THE ETHICAL DIMENSIONS OF THE TEACHING PROFESSION

Yunus Yildiz

Department of English Language Teaching, Tishk International University, Near baz, Erbil, KRG, Iraq
E-mail: yunus.yildiz@tiu.edu.iq
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4471-457X>

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ABSTRACT

The Ethics is a branch of philosophy that examines the principles at the basis of human behavior and discusses concepts such as good, bad, right, and wrong. Teachers need to be made aware of the ethical responsibilities that come with their jobs so that they can act with greater awareness and sensitivity in the classroom, which will improve the overall quality of their interactions with students. Teachers are able to enhance their students' learning, evaluate them in a variety of ways, and give them the opportunity to learn specific material when they organize a variety of activities in the classroom. In order to make the educational process more efficient, educators should conduct themselves with ethical awareness. As a consequence of this, members of the academic community, members of the general public, and teachers can acknowledge the significance of the ethical component of teaching. This article aims to discuss the main reasons that make the teaching profession the subject of ethics, considering the opinions compiled from the literature and increasing the sensitivity of educators on this issue. This article aims to discuss the main reasons that make the teaching profession the subject of ethics, considering the opinions compiled from the literature and increasing the sensitivity of educators on this issue.

The object of research: Emphasis on ethics is a word we hear in every cornerstone of life, and it is a word that is taken together with manners and decency. Therefore, it is high time to review ethics in teaching to interested readers. The object of this study is to revise the related literature on the concept of ethics and compile significant features in one study.

Problem description: Since ethics is a paramount issue in education, issues such as the ethical dimensions of teaching and what is useful in the teaching profession for teachers or candidates who think of the profession as a sacred duty, teacher-student interaction, the foundations on which educational plans are based, and the ethical aspects of teacher attitudes needs to be investigated.

Suggested solution to the problem: According to the findings of the research, the ethical dimension can be influenced by a number of factors, some of which include the interactions between teachers and students, educational initiatives, the attitudes of teachers, classroom restrictions, and the majority of instructional decisions. As a result, in order to make the process of education more effective, educators should model ethical behavior in their own lives

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1. Introduction

1.1. The object of research

Decency and morality are two words that are sometimes used interchangeably, and we hear them both frequently. As a result, it is time for those who are interested to study a refresher on teaching ethics. In order to remind educators of the importance of their responsibility and the importance of the notion of ethics in education, this study will evaluate the relevant literature and highlight the most essential issues.

1.2. Problem description

Throughout history, various thinkers have discussed the concepts to which people ascribe positive or negative values and have pursued good and virtue under the roof of ethics. In recent years, professional ethics have been widely discussed in the western world. Accordingly, individuals working in institutions are expected to work within the framework of ethical rules.

By its very nature, teaching is also involved in these debates, and a limited number of educators try to establish the profession's ethical principles. As has been insisted upon by many thinkers for centuries, ethics is an integral part of teaching. This fact is kept on the agenda by contemporary thinkers and educators as well as historical figures such as Plato, Confucius, Aristotle, Avicenna, Al-Farabi and Buddha [1–3]. Teaching takes place in an ethical context, not due to certain factors; teaching is ethical because it involves human behavior and relationships [4]. Teachers try to influence students knowingly and especially in a positive way [5]. They do this when they prefer a certain behavior to others, they believe to be good, righteous, just, and virtuous. Almost all teacher behavior can have an ethical meaning; asking a student a question, sharing information about a student with another colleague, and setting rules in the classroom about who will do a certain activity first and who will do it later is just a few of these [6]. Although the teacher is unaware of the ethical dimension of their behavior and its consequences, all their behaviors and the ethical messages contained in these behaviors affect the students [7].

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem

Understanding the ethical dimensions of the teaching profession is a critical issue for all teachers. As easily guessed, the teacher's behavior forms a model for the students and can be reflected in the student's behavior [8, 9]. Nor is it about the teacher following any values education program. Although a teacher does not focus on any value during teaching activities, the teacher's behavior contains implicit ethical meanings and affects all students in this class [10, 11]. Ethical behavior is shaped by the character of the teacher, the overall atmosphere and goals of the school, teaching methods, or the content taught [12]. Therefore, teachers should be aware of the ethical consequences of their behavior in the classroom and think about them [13]. However, in a descriptive study by [14], most participating teachers stated that they did not have much opportunity to reflect on the ethical dimensions or ethical decisions of their behavior in their daily lives. The duty of teaching, accepted as a sacred duty in religious literature, is kept the same as the work of the prophets because one of the duties of the prophets is to tell humanity what is beautiful and beneficial and to invite them to that path [15]. Today, teachers who complain that they do not receive a good salary groan about the work-life brings and the lack of time they spare for themselves [16]. Therefore, it is important that at least the candidates who step into the teaching profession are given the ethical dimensions of the profession, living for someone else. The principles, such as the happiness of others, will bring happiness to the educator during their education because teaching is not growing potatoes in the field or fishing in the lake [17].

Although it directly impacts teaching processes, the ethical dimension is often neglected in teacher training programs [6, 18]. Today's teacher education programs generally focus on teaching technical aspects, providing the necessary skills and knowledge. Although much research on ethics and education is written in general terms, teacher education programs still do not include courses that include the ethical dimensions of the profession [19]. This fact can cause teachers to ignore the ethical dimension of their educational behavior or prevent them from effectively resolving their ethical dilemmas.

2. Materials and Methods

This study made use of both primary and secondary resources. The researcher gathered secondary data by consulting already published literature on the subject of ethics in the teaching profession and conducting literature reviews. This served as the base knowledge for the research.

The bulk of this work's data came from articles with the title and content of ethics in the teaching profession published in peer-reviewed journals, as well as articles containing the author's previously published works, reflecting the work's focus on ethics in education and the ethical dimensions of the teaching profession. This research aimed to answer questions like, "What is ethics from the perspective of teachers?", "Why is ethics important in education?", "What is the role of educators in the eyes of students?", and "How does this affect students' moral development in the context of teacher-student relations?».».

This paper was constructed utilizing the aforementioned library materials, online sources, and print/online articles.

The article discussed the significance of exploiting the individuality of teachers to promote values in pupils such as self-sacrifice, correctness, punctuality, dignity, honesty, and leadership. This is accomplished by exposing students to the teachers' personalities. Teachers that are interested in helping their pupils develop strong scientific and moral values might utilize the study's findings as a quick reference.

3. Result

3. 1. Ethics in Teaching

Although teaching the first guidance of the individual in education is considered a duty of the mother and father [20], teachers largely must provide education for the new generation living in this age of technology [21]. Because the world of ideas that the student lives in and the world of ideas that the parents live in is different. Trained teachers are the ones who can understand the students at this point. Some authors who have expressed an opinion on the ethical dimensions of teaching have all constructed an understanding of teaching as first and foremost a moral activity [22, 23].

The existing literature on moral teaching has identified two main ways teachers' teaching is a moral activity [5, 24]. First, teaching is founded upon a relationship between two or more individuals. Second, teachers are engaged in changing the behavior of others to attain prescribed ends. The relationship between teacher and student in the teaching profession is essentially ethical. Classroom interactions involve ethical decisions, and teachers work with young people and children who need their guidance and care. Classroom relationships, dialogues, and interactions have shown that the relationship between teacher and student is based on an unequal presence of power. In this relationship, the teacher is the authority figure in the classroom and has to make complex ethical decisions in very short periods [25]. In the teacher-student relationship, the teacher is given the task and authority to supervise the student, guide him/her in the desired way, to support his/her self-efficacy and independence. By undertaking this task, the teacher also accepts an ethical responsibility on the student [26]. By assigning the teacher the important responsibility of directing the development of a growing individual, society agrees that the teacher assumes the dominant role in this relationship. But this dominant role can lead to the occasional abuse and ethically controversial practices often seen in the environment [27]. Therefore, the ethical responsibility given to teachers for students' mental and social development should be to the extent that they can base their authority on justified grounds, and teachers should be open to supervision concerning their profession.

The work that is the responsibility of the teacher is the transfer of knowledge to the student [28]. In this context, the teacher uses many methods while ensuring that the student has knowledge and experience about a certain subject. For example, he/she gives examples from his/her own life, tells stories, shows educational and instructive videos, and sometimes includes them in educational trips and asks the students for their ideas through them, respects their thoughts, and corrects any mistakes; it states the exceptions that exist with generalizations, determines the topics and skills to be learned new, and tries to make the topic more meaningful and interesting for the students. All these and many others are methods and activities the teacher applies using his/her position [3, 29, 30]. Even in more democratic cases where decisions about learning and classroom arrangements are made jointly with the students, that is, when the teacher shares authority with the students, the position of the teacher is at least as effective as in classrooms where the teacher makes all decisions. Because in both cases, decisions are always made in line with the teacher's goals, and in democratic classrooms, the teacher teaches students to make independent and democratic decisions [31].

In contrast, the teacher who always makes the decisions teaches his/her students to depend on the teacher or the leader. So, in both cases, the teacher's dominant position vis-à-vis the student is equally obvious. By institutionalizing teaching as a profession, society approves this authority of the teacher on the one hand and, on the other hand, determines and limits how this authority is used by setting ethical principles [32].

The second factor that characterizes teaching as an ethical situation is teaching curricula [18]. Generally, teaching techniques and plans constitute two basic aspects of school educational activities [33, 34]. The curriculum determines the size and content of the training provided. The ethical dimension of the curriculum is preferred according to the culture and other possible con-

tent options by considering the culture and country realities of certain contents when preparing a plan [35, 36]. Therefore, the content to be selected should aim to create useful learning in the student. In other words, teachers teach certain knowledge and skills because they believe they are valuable and that, because of this learning, students will become better and more useful individuals. These choices, the philosophy on which these choices are based, and the ethical messages conveyed in this way affect students' personal development and, therefore, their lives.

3. 2. Teacher Attitudes

Teacher's authority over his/her students and control of the classroom is not the main reason that makes the profession the subject of ethical science. Teaching is an ethical activity because teachers have a responsibility to support the moral development of their students in the most appropriate and correct way [37]. The most important factor in supporting this development is the general attitude of the teacher in the classroom. The ethical character of a teacher can be thought of as a manner and that this permeates all aspects of the teacher's behavior in the classroom [38].

The exemplary representation of the teachers' aspects in line with ethical principles is at least as important for their success in their work as their mastery of the subject they teach and their ability to lecture. For the student to gain a second nature or to establish his/her personality, the attitudes of his/her environment, friends, and even teachers are as important as the education he/she receives in the family. Teachers must possess certain qualities such as honesty, altruism, generosity, and diligence; otherwise, they cannot expect these and similar qualities from their students. Students, too, have attitudes that exhibit their level of moral development, which is expected to rise due to their interactions with the teacher and the subject they are expected to learn.

[39] notes that what constitutes the essence of teaching, in other words, any activity of a teacher that may concern students can be the subject of ethics. Therefore, teachers must always consider what is good, right, and virtuous. As a result, the compliance of teachers' behavior with ethical principles significantly affects the ethical dimension of students' behavior. There are three situations in which teachers can ethically influence students through their behavior [40]. First, teachers can explain to students in a didactic language what they should or shouldn't do, which can turn into indoctrination. Secondly, they can teach ethical behavior, such as religious leaders or a professor giving lectures on the subject, or finally, they can model their behavior by following ethical principles. The first two methods have limited effects on students' lives. The third method has more power to shape students' behavior and influence them efficiently in an educational sense. In this way, the teacher shows them how to be fair while at the same time being fair to them and expects fair treatment from them as well; while valuing them and treating them compassionately, he/she expects them to do the same; it becomes a model for how to be tolerant by treating them with tolerance.

3. 3. In-Class Rules and Ethics

Another issue in the ethical dimensions of teaching is classroom rules. Classroom rules are specified by the teacher or determined within the school directorate and must be followed. Classroom rules are the most basic tool for regulating teacher and student relationships. In creating and implementing these rules, numerous opportunities arise to teach students certain ethical values [41, 42]. Classroom rules, beyond their simple functions of organizing the classroom, disciplining and managing students, reflect the teacher's thoughts about students and their outlook on life, which can play an important role. Basically, these rules reflect the ethical order of the world and a way of life [43]. Rules are often surface appearances of more general ethical principles and reflect the teacher's perspective on their role in the classroom [44]. Strict rules, such as not harming others, accepting everyone in their position, keeping their word, not stealing, or listening quietly while the teacher speaks, reflect the teacher's effort to positively shape students' behavior and embed the ethical principles in which they believe in the classroom.

3. 4. Teacher-Student Interactions

Teacher-student interactions are another factor that serves a key function in carrying ethical messages within the classroom and supporting students' moral development [45]. As a result of the analysis of many classroom events and teacher-student interactions, classrooms are filled with

numerous events with ethical implications and messages and that teacher-student interaction is the primary tool for communicating ethical messages through words, behaviors, and a wide variety of modes of expression [46]. [47] point out that ethical connotations are often incomprehensible at first glance, and that teachers, who are best aware of the complex dynamics in their classrooms, need to develop an awareness of these ethical sensitivities in classroom life.

[37] mention three main factors that make teaching the subject of ethics. The first is that teaching is based on relations between people and that all human relations can be the subject of ethics. The second factor is that teachers act to change students positively. As it is known, the concepts of good, bad, or better and worse are always the subject of ethics. In addition to these two factors, Bill Johnston mentions that many of the decisions teachers make in the classroom have ethical dimensions; for example, what assignment to assign to students, how to grade assignments, or how to deal with a student who disrupts the class order are all topics in an ethical context. The author says that research in educational sciences can only help teachers to a limited extent and that most classroom decisions align with the teacher's personal preferences. These decisions are the subject of ethical science because they are based on the teacher's beliefs about what is good, right, and beautiful.

3. 5. Processes Spent in Making Ethical Decisions

When the literature is examined, it is seen that teachers act under the influence of utilitarian-consequentialist or non-consequentialist approaches when making ethical decisions [48]. Utilitarian-consequentialist approaches consider the possible consequences of behavior on others when determining its ethical value. The best solution strategy at any decision stage is to choose the option that provides the most benefit to the individual among the behavioral options. Doing the right thing requires first identifying and reviewing the behavioral options that exist in the current situation and choosing the one that produces the best outcomes for everyone. Naturally, every option can have positive outcomes, but a teacher who adopts this approach must select the option with the best combination of outcomes and act as required by that option [49]. Critics of this practical approach are also used to examine the teaching profession from an ethical point of view. Because the proponents of this approach evaluate the teaching experience in the context of a set of educational skills or behavioral changes aimed at the end of this process, in other words, teaching is seen only as a means of achieving certain outcomes, such as imparting some basic scientific knowledge to students, imparting them with social skills, or preparing them for their future professions [50]. The basic ethical assumption of this approach is that all these outcomes envisaged for students are for their good. To make accurate calculations in mathematics daily shopping, learning botany, caring for field crops, or training any branch, is always considered in this context. Proponents of this view consider teaching to be either a transfer of knowledge to students or a process of revealing students' interests and abilities [51]. Ultimately, what is ethical in both cases is to see the desired behavioral changes in students.

On the other hand, [52] disagree with this view and question it, with the support of philosophers such as Socrates, Kant, and Dewey. This "means or processes leading to the end" approach is problematic and far from grasping and representing the essence of teaching. Doing so reduces teaching to the position of being a means or "price" paid for the means or purposes that achieve the set ends and ignores the fact that the teacher has intrinsic value to their existence as an individual and the work done. In other words, a machine or any technological device may well do the job. According to him, such an approach sees teachers and teaching as tools of a purpose that exists independently of themselves and ignores the fact that they have value.

Non-consequential approaches, on the other hand, emphasize the duties and obligations and the principles to be followed when discussing the ethical value of behavior [53]. The ethical value of behavior must be sought in its internal dynamics and characteristics, regardless of its consequences. [54], quoting Kant, says that people are inherently valuable and respectable because they can act ethically. In other words, the main reason for good, righteous, and beautiful behavior is not the manipulation of our instincts, such as having a certain power, having an experience that gives us pleasure, or avoiding pain. It's also much more than simple reactions to what's being done, what's going on in the environment, or just waiting for things to happen spontaneously. Because of this capacity to act ethically or morally, Kant says that being human is a goal and that no human being can

be characterized as a means that serves a purpose that only someone else has constructed. Human beings, who are ethical beings who can live in an ethical world of their creation, have an inherent value, and there can be no “counterpart” to it. It is also very important what kind of life people want for themselves, and there is no equivalent to an ethnically based life that Kant idealized, in which all people treat each other with the idea that they have value. In this regard, Kant criticizes the practical approach, which proposes elaborate pre-arranged criteria for the realization of human desires. Instead, he proposes to focus on how human beings can glorify their existence with the potential to recognize and understand moral behavior. This aim is related to the intention of the person doing the behavior and the factors that motivate him/her. If the behavior is set out with good intentions, the behavior in question can also be considered ethically good. In this context, a teacher, if he/she is in any decision-making process, should consider universal principles and values such as truthfulness, justice, courage, friendship, and compassion rather than the consequences of his/her decision [5]. Therefore, teachers and their educational mission should be considered in this context from an ethical point of view since it includes the human factor, which is the subject of ethics.

4. Discussion

We have evaluated the issues such as what is ethics and what is useful in the teaching profession from the perspective of different researchers point of views regarding the ethical dimensions of teaching, teacher-student interaction, the foundations on which educational plans are based, and the ethical aspects of teacher attitudes. In short, almost every moment of teachers needs evaluation in an ethical context, and the necessity of educators’ sensitivity to the subject has been emphasized. Today, what is written and done on teaching and ethics is in the form of examining the ethical rules that should be followed by individuals entering the profession and proposing behavior and attitude patterns that can be considered ethically appropriate. On the other hand, the principles on which the proposed behavior patterns are based, how they emerge, and why the teaching profession is so intertwined with ethics have not been adequately examined. Considering all the conditions in the school environment, implementing the right behaviour and attitude in teaching is not as easy and proper for the teacher or the student. Educators must have a strong sense of service and diplomacy to deal with the students and should deliver a clear message [55]. We can say that ethics in teaching, which advocates improving character education by implementing school rules or working environment, has brought a certain innovation to teaching/education [47]. However, it is impossible to say that ethics has become widespread globally as an application in schools. Therefore, the teacher should follow ethical rules according to cultural values and sometimes according to his/her instincts.

Teaching is both a mental and an ethical act, and these two dimensions always exist simultaneously. The effects of these two dimensions on students are also simultaneous and cannot be considered independently of each other. Education research has shown that factors such as teacher-student interaction, educational programs, teachers’ attitudes, classroom rules, and most of the decisions teachers make in the classroom can be related to the ethical dimension. According to some authors, this dimension is hidden in the results of what teachers say or do, while others find its place in the internal processes of man, who is an ethical entity in his/her own right. Either way, recognizing the ethical dimension of teaching isn’t always easy and often requires active consciousness and effort. However, the effects of the ethical dimension of teaching on students are always in question and play a role in shaping their character.

This study is research obtained by literature review. The author could have enriched the research with quantitative data by taking the opinions of teachers or students in his work settings.

5. Conclusion

In summary, the ethical dimension of the profession should be recognized by teachers so that they can be more aware and sensitive in their behavior, and the quality of their interactions in the classroom can increase. By organizing various activities in the classroom, teachers can stimulate their students, evaluate them in many respects, and enable them to learn certain information. Teachers should act with ethical sensitivity to create a more effective educational process. As a result, academics, the public, and teachers can accept the importance of the ethical dimension of teaching.

Conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining, and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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